

Evaluation of Ziram as repellent against house rats

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The house rat, *Rattus rattus* is one of the major rodent pest causing immense losses in storage directly through feeding on stored commodities and structural damage besides contaminating the stored products with its urine and feces. In storage, rodents account for 2.5% losses and therefore require effective management strategies. For management of house rats, it is imperative to use chemicals which are effective against the pest rodents and safe to non-targets. Rodent repellents could be an effective tool in such situations. In the present study efficacy of Ziram, a dithiocarbamate fungicide was evaluated for its repellent effects against house rats, *Rattus rattus* under bi-choice, multi-choice and simulated storage conditions. The test animal was exposed to 2 and 3% Ziram treated pearl millet bait with plain pearl millet food in bi-choice test in iron mesh cage for seven days and 3% Ziram treated pearl millet food in multi-choice long with plain wheat, jowar and pearl millet in plus maze for four days. In bi-choice trial the treated bait (2 and 3% conc. in pearl millet) was completely rejected by the test rodents whereas the alternative plain bait was consumed in the range of 4.19 to 4.67 and 4.37 to 5.23g/100g body wt when offered with treated bait at 2 and 3%, respectively during 7 day long test period. In multi-choice test the arm with Ziram 3% treated pearl millet bait was visited least (for 37 seconds/30 min), whereas, the arm with plain pearl millet bait was visited maximum (18.25 visits for 15.25 minutes/30 minutes) followed by the arms with jowar (9.25 visits of 4.0 min/30 min.) and wheat (7.25 visits for 3.50 min/30 min.). Under simulated storage condition, two experimental sets were maintained, in one set stacked grain filled bags were sprayed with ziram 3% and in other set ziram (3%) was applied on wall and floor of cage. One healthy house rat was released in each cage and its response was observed for seven days. In both the experimental conditions the test rodent foraged around the bags but never tried to damage the gunny bags for feeding on grains stored in it and died due to starvation on 5th day in one of the experimental sets. These findings therefore revealed that Ziram possesses repellent effects on house rats at least for a week.

Antixenotic and allelochemical resistance traits of ridge gourd [*Luffa acutangula* (Roxb.) L.] against melon fruit fly (*Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett)) in arid region of Rajasthan

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Plants genotypes possess different antixenotic and/or allelochemical properties, which resultantly induce in them different mechanisms of resistance. Various phenotypic traits including length of ovary pubescence, rind hardness, rind thickness, fruit length, fibre content, and fruit diameter and allelochemical traits including flavonoid content, ascorbic

acid, free amino acid, tannins content, and phenols content of fruit were studied on fifteen varieties/genotypes of ridge gourd, *L. acutangulain* relation to resistance against *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett) under field conditions in the hot arid region of India. The larval density per fruit had a significant positive correlation with percentage fruit infestation ($r = 0.96$; $p < 0.01$). AHRG-29, AHRG-57 and Pusa Nasdar were the most resistant; Arka Sujata, AHRG-36, AHRG-41, S. Manjari, S. Uphal, AHRG-35, Jaipuri Long, AHRG-56, AHRG-53, AHRG-46 and AHRG-48 were moderately resistant; AHRG-49, AHRG-33, AHRG-42, AHRG-30, AHRG- 23, AHRG-58, AHRG-50, AHRG-28, AHRG-43, AHRG-52 and AHRG-59 were susceptible whereas AHRG-47, AHRG-31, AHRG-48 and AHRG-61 were the highly susceptible varieties/genotypes against fruit fly. The larval densities ranged from 9.97 to 19.10 larvae per fruit and significantly lower in resistant varieties/genotypes than the susceptible varieties/genotypes. The larval density was highest in genotype AHRG-31 (29.27 larvae fruit⁻¹) followed by AHRG-61 (28.6 larvae fruit⁻¹). The minimum larval density was found in AHRG-57 (13.6 larvae fruit⁻¹) followed by Pusa Nasdar (14.77 larvae fruit⁻¹). The per cent fruit infestation was highest in AHRG-31 (80.47%) and lowest in AHRG-57 (16.47%) followed by AHRG-29 (18.13%). The length of ovary pubescence, rind hardness, fibre content and rind thickness ranged from 0.17 to 0.50 mm, 2.37 to 6.68 kg cm⁻², 1.17 to 2.28 g 100g⁻¹ edible fruit and 0.56 to 1.07 mm, respectively, being significantly high in resistant and low in susceptible varieties/genotypes. However, the fruit length (3.67 to 29.70 cm) and fruit diameter (3.35 to 6.53 cm) being significantly low in resistant and high in susceptible varieties/genotypes. The free amino acid of different varieties/genotypes fruits ranged from 3.36 to 5.77 (mgg⁻¹ on dry weight basis) with values significantly lower in resistant and higher in susceptible varieties/genotypes. Flavonoids, tannins, phenols and ascorbic acid contents ranged from 1.31 to 2.37 mg 100 g⁻¹, 6.64 to 9.49 mg100g⁻¹, 40.90 to 72.34 mg g⁻¹ and 310.95 to 497.18 mg 10 g⁻¹, respectively with values significantly higher in resistant and lower in susceptible varieties/genotypes. Free amino acid was lowest in resistant and highest in susceptible varieties/genotypes whereas phenols, tannin, ascorbic acid and flavonoid contents were highest in resistant and lowest in susceptible varieties/genotypes.

Exogenous application of salicylic acid and its derivatives improves antioxidant defense mechanism, growth and yield of clusterbean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L.) under water limiting environment

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Exposure of plants to water stress leads to serious physiological and biochemical dysfunctions including reduction in growth, photosynthesis and damages of cellular components. Seed priming has proved to be an effective method in imparting stress tolerance to plants. Seed priming is the induction of a particular physiological state in